

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 2.3

Website with data information, description of available and emerging web services and user client to find data regardless their location and regular updates on datasets that have been FAIRified

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Project

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Work package 2

Bringing the Arctic Data System into action

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1. Introduction

The Arctic PASSION project is described in more detail in the project website which is available at <https://arcticpassion.eu/>. The purpose of Arctic PASSION is creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. This implies integrating already existing observing systems in a system of systems approach as well addressing gaps in the current observing system. Arctic PASSION will generate data through the project implementation, but equally important is to map and establish access to already existing datasets in support of the pilot services and other activities of Arctic PASSION.

Arctic PASSION will exploit existing data in the region. In particular operational meteorological data made available through WMO Global Telecommunication System (GTS) will be important for the model experiments. No full overview of third party data that will be used is currently available.

In order to support the other work packages and the overall objective of Arctic PASSION, a website containing a human interface to the data catalogue and guidance material for data providers is established. This document provides information on the website. The relevant information on the scope for this deliverable is provided in [\[RD-1\]](#) and [\[RD-2\]](#).

1.1. Applicable documents

- [RD-1]** D2.1 Data Management Plan,
- [RD-2]** D2.2 Report on the interoperability status of Copernicus services in light of EU regulations and Polar Data System Architecture
- [RD-3]** Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.
- [RD-4]** MET Norway Metadata Specification, <https://github.com/metno/mmd/blob/master/doc/mmd-specification.pdf>

2. Purpose of the website

The website will provide information on available datasets through a data catalogue. This data catalogue will have a human interface that is integrated in the website where data consumers can discover and access relevant datasets. The data catalogue will be populated through harvesting of information from relevant data centres (see e.g. [\[RD-2\]](#)), existing and new, which fulfill the technical requirements for the exchange of discovery metadata. These technical requirements will also be outlined in [\[RD-1\]](#). Furthermore, the website will contain detailed guidance material on how to properly encode datasets in a FAIR manner [\[RD-3\]](#), which interactive and machine interfaces (services) the project provides, etc...

3. Relation to SAON activities

Arctic PASSION is a European contribution to GEOSS and SAON (<https://arcticobserving.org/>). As SAON already operates a data portal (<https://saon.met.no/>, available through the menu item "Services" in the SAON website, see [Figure 1](#)) a dialogue with SAON was initiated to reuse this website in the context of Arctic PASSION. This will improve the operational context of the SAON data portal and ensure a broad footprint of Arctic PASSION data management activities in the SAON community. In order to link this activity to Arctic PASSION, some graphical elements of Arctic PASSION and information on the Arctic PASSION project will be added to the website.

4. Implementation of website

The website ([Figure 1](#)) is implemented using a standard Content Management System (CMS) solution named Drupal (<https://www.drupal.org/>). The CMS chosen is flexible and provides a mature and rich list of modules that can be easily installed to add or enhance features of the portal. Additionally it allows for local development, which can be done to fulfill specific needs, building additional services or ad-hoc functionalities. Currently the website is running Drupal 8 and will soon be upgraded to the latest Drupal 9 release. The chosen solution also allows for collaboration on content creation and editing in a larger community. In the current version a local user registry is used, but work is in progress to link this with Single Sign On (SSO) through several identity providers, such as Edugain, Google, github, Microsoft and ORCID. At the present stage login is required only for selected processing services. Functionality of the data catalogue is achieved through integration of backend services in the CMS. For example, data visualization and interaction widgets returned by the plotting service are embedded within the pages of the website, while fast and dynamic updates of search results on the data catalogue (with filters and facets) are achieved through communication with the search server.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the SAON Data Portal.

5. Content of the website

5.1. Data catalogue

The data catalogue (Figure 2) is populated through harvesting of discovery metadata from data centres operated by Arctic PASSION partners and others. The interactive interface to the catalogue allows data consumers to search for, retrieve and visualise/transform (see Figure 3 and Figure 4) data found. The map service illustrated in Figure 3 allows navigation of all 4 dimensions of the dataset. The various layers in the dataset can be activated or not and transparency modified. Similarly, timeseries is visualised as illustrated by Figure 4 which supports dynamic visualisation, direct readout of values and saving the current status of the illustration.

At the time of writing the report, information is harvested using OAI-PMH and OGC CSW, serving discovery metadata in ISO19115 (various flavours, including WMO and INSPIRE) or GCMD DIF. The data centres that are harvested currently are indicated in Figure 5, where solid lines reflect active harvesting of discovery metadata and broken lines reflect harvesting in progress. The harvesting process in

continuously being updated and support for DCAT and schema.org approaches is under development. Details of the harvesting status is left out of this document due to the continuous nature of the activity.

Figure 2. The interactive search interface of the SAON Data Portal.

Home / METSIS OL6 WMS

Figure 3. The Web Map Service embedded in the data portal exemplified by visualisation of potential temperature from a numerical ocean model.

Data access:

Add to Basket

Show extended metadata

Visualise TimeSeries

Download as ASCII

OPeNDAP

Export MMD

Access: Free

TA

Figure 4. The timeseries visualisation embedded in the data portal exemplified by visualisation of temperature from a WMO meteorological station.

Figure 5. Outline of data centres being harvested and ingested in the data catalogue today. Solid lines indicate active harvesting and ingestion, broken lines, harvesting in progress, but interfaces are yet not fully functional.

The information harvested is transformed into the information model outlined in Figure 6 and described in more detail in [RD-4]. [RD-4] describes an XML implementation of the information model used, but the information is ingested in various searchable systems for practical use in the data catalogue. Figure 6 indicates the logical structure and the purpose of this illustration is merely to indicate the information elements being used in the information model and through this indicate capacities possible to offer in a data catalogue. Practical utilisation of this information model will at any time depend on the information received from data centres which is on a general basis suboptimal. The information harvested and transformed into this information model is made available through various technical systems. Specifically SolR [https://solr.apache.org/] is used to serve interactive users through the website while pyCSW [https://pycsw.org/] is used for machine access to the catalogue. The machine interfaces offered to external users that would like to consume information from the catalogue include OAI-PMH, OGC CSW, OpenSearch and RESTful services. Only OAI-PMH and OGC CSW is currently well tested and MET is working with the OSGeo community to further improve the performance of pyCSW. In particular, work is undertaken to improve the information handling. Application Programming Interfaces are generally working well.

NOTE | The pyCSW implementation is still under development.

Figure 6. Logical outline of the information model used by the data catalogue.

5.2. Guidance material

5.2.1. Introduction

The guidance material developed for Arctic PASSION data providers and in support of the SAON Data Portal in general is located in a dedicated section which is accessible through the menu item marked "Support" (see Figure 7). The material is still under development, but initial material and background information is provided. The purpose of this information is to ensure that data and web services are published using standardised approaches which is necessary to build services on top of the data. Without such standardisation, the degrees of freedom is too large and it is impossible to establish efficient reuse of data and services. This effort within Arctic PASSION is primarily addressing the I and the R in the FAIR guiding principles [RD-3]. I.e. making data and services Interoperable and Reuseable.

Figure 7. Screenshot of the menu item giving access to the guidance material in preparation for Arctic PASSION.

5.2.2. FAIR Encoding of Data

Arctic PASSION is promoting self-describing data formats like NetCDF according to the Climate and Forecast Conventions or Darwin Core Archives.

CF-NetCDF

NetCDF adhering to the [Climate and Forecast Conventions](http://cfconventions.org/index.html) [http://cfconventions.org/index.html] is widely used, both in the oceanographic community, in the Earth System Grid Federation, in Copernicus services, by ESA and EUMETSAT for Sentinel data provision and WMO is developing WMO specific profiles of the standard. By adding the [Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery](https://adc.met.no/node/4) [https://adc.met.no/node/4], discovery level metadata can be embedded in the datasets.

Darwin Core Archive

According to the [Darwin Core Archive Assistant](http://tools.gbif.org/dwca-assistant/) [http://tools.gbif.org/dwca-assistant/] *Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A)* is a Biodiversity informatics data standard that makes use of the Darwin Core terms to produce

a single, self contained dataset for species occurrence or taxonomic (species) data. It is the preferred format for publishing data to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility. You export your data as a set of one or more text (CSV) files. A simple XML descriptor file (called meta.xml) is required to inform others how your files are organized.

Data that doesn't fit into these categories will be accompanied by a detailed product manual providing guidance to data consumers. These data will require some more human effort to utilise. Both CF and DwC-A standards are managed in well defined governance processes and the standards are used widely beyond the original user communities.

Details on how to use these standards as well as guidance on granularity issues will be added to the website as it evolves. As a general recommendation it is recommended to publish data at a relatively high level of granularity and rather add requested grouping as virtual dataset. E.g. instead of publishing all CTD casts from a research cruise as one dataset, an approach that suits the observing people well, but e.g. modelers less, it is recommended to publish individual casts and rather to group these through a virtual parent record that represents the cruise. With this approach it is relatively easy for various communities to find the information needed.

5.2.3. Web services

Arctic PASSION develops services utilising some web services. In the current situation support is enabled for OGC WMS and OPeNDAP.

OGC WMS is used to visualise information on maps. This could be satellite imagery, numerical simulations of the atmosphere or the ocean or other information suitable for presentation in a map service. Details on which map projections that should be supported will be provided later. If multiple products are attempted to be presented in the same map, the common map projection selected. In worst case, this is not a map projection that is suitable for high latitudes.

OPeNDAP is used for dynamic visualisation of timeseries (see e.g. [Figure 4](#)), profiles etc. In the current situation, only the timeseries visualisation is enabled. All these services will require data to be represented by the [Discrete sampling geometries](#) [<http://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-conventions/cf-conventions-1.9/cf-conventions.html#discrete-sampling-geometries>] approach of CF-NetCDF.

6. Future perspectives of website with data portal

The life span of project specific websites is generally limited. By reusing the existing SAON Data Portal which is supported by a number of projects through time, sustained operation of the data portal and the accompanying services is ensured.

The SAON Data Portal was established following the International Polar Year (IPY) and is maintained as an add on to the legacy [Arctic Data Center](#) [<https://adc.met.no/>] (ADC) which the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET) established to support international operational data coordination and national data management during IPY. ADC is also the MET contribution to infrastructure projects [Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System](#) [<https://www.sios-svalbard.org/>] (SIOS), [Norwegian Scientific Data Network](#) [<https://www.nordatanet.no/>] (NorDataNet), [Norwegian Marine Data Centre](#) [<https://www.nmdc.no/>] (NMDC) and

is linked with the [National ground Segment for Satellite data in Norway](https://satellitdata.no/) [https://satellitdata.no/]. Through this sustained operation of the data portal is ensured beyond the life time of the project.
